

TIME MANAGEMENT BEHAVIOR AS PREDICTOR OF PERCEIVED CONTROL OF TIME AND LIFE SATISFACTION AMONG STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Effective time management skills, such as planning, prioritization, and scheduling, are hypothesized to enhance perceived control over time. This increased perceived control is then expected to contribute to greater life satisfaction by reducing stress, increasing self-efficacy, and improving mood. This research investigates the time management behavior as predictor of perceived control of time and life satisfaction among students. A sample of 300 college and university students were selected from district Murree. Purposive sampling technique was used for data collection. The instruments, Time Management Self-Assessment Questionnaire (Olmstead, 2010), Perceived Control of Internal States Scale (Pallant, 2000) and Students' Life Satisfaction Scale (Huebner et al., 2022) were used. SPSS (Version-27) was used for data collection. Results revealed that time management behavior as predictor of perceived control of time, and life satisfaction among students. The study has implications for students and teachers with reference to their academic productivity.

Keywords: Time Management Behaviors, Perceived Control of Time, Life Satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most valuable assets is time that must be carefully planned and managed in order to be successful and productive in life. In this competitive world we inhabit to motivate individuals to efficiently plan and manage their time in order to fortify themselves. Because of how quickly people's lives are moving, Silva & Wetzel (2007) view it as an issue in daily life. Manktelow and Anand (2008) believe the same thing while Tracy (2000) views time as the secret to both personal and professional success. Helms and Ettkin (2000) view it as a weapon for competition. Olmstead (2010) views time as a useful resource for this and is the primary driver of efficient time management as well. However, behavior is the way people engage with their surroundings, such as social or ecological events or activities (Uher, 2016).

Other terms that had nearly the same meaning as time management were also used interchangeably, including time structure (Bond & Feather, 1988). We found this challenging to ascertain the precise nature of time management in previous studies (Mackenzie & Nickerson, 2009), to characterize the present situation, and to pinpoint what aspect of time management is accountable for which outcomes due to the absence of a widely recognized definition of the concept. Finding time for the things you need or want to complete can therefore be facilitated by effective time management (Sandberg, 2004). Time management, according to Bartholomew (2013), is a collection of abilities, resources, and methods used to schedule time for completing particular tasks, such as (Grissom et al., 2015). The connection between time management, perceived

control over time and life satisfaction is complex and reciprocal. When we effectively manage our time, we can feel more in control of it, which can increase our happiness. However, a distorted view of our own time may hinder us from effectively managing it, so reducing our degree of life pleasure.

For instance, if we frequently underestimate the amount of time required for tasks, ongoing stress and disappointment may lead to a lower degree of life satisfaction. On the other side, if we learn to honestly evaluate our time constraints and appropriately prioritize our responsibilities, we may feel more in control of and content with our life. Although time management is crucial for everyone, college students who are not under their parents' constant supervision need to pay particular attention to it. However, many college students complain about not having enough time to finish assignments and other learning tasks for their classes. According to Elkind (2012), Arnold Bennett was among the first proponents of time management techniques at the turn of the 20th century with his book "How to Live on Twenty-Four Hours a Day" published in 1907. The process of planning, organizing, and controlling time in order to accomplish more and better work in less time is referred to as time management.

It is stated that "behavior that aim at achieving an effective use of time while performing certain goal-directed activities (Claessens et al., 2007)" and "practices intended to maximize intellectual productivity (Britton and Tesser, 1991)." One technique to monitor and control time is through time management (Eilam & Aharon, 2003). Clusters of behavioral skills that are crucial for organizing study and course load are known as time management (Lay & Schouwenburg, 1993). Time management abilities can be thought of as self-regulation in the temporal domain (Claessens et al., 2007) and are defined as an employee's capacity to organize activities, create and prioritize goals, and track the status of their work (Peeters & Rutte, 2005). These abilities assist workers in taking charge of their work encouraging and guiding others toward an objective and cutting down on time wastage (Claessens et al., 2007). Because creating explicit performance goals

boosts task interest and dedication, goal setting can also assist employees overcome the detrimental effects of boredom (Meyer et al., 2004).

Despite time management's widespread use, not much scientific study has been done on how People are able to manage their time and the procedures that go along with it. Despite occasionally conflicting findings, the review showed that time management practices were typically found to have a beneficial impact on perceived control over one's time, health, academic or professional performance, work happiness, and stress reduction. There was some indication of individual variations in time management. Although it has been demonstrated that time management training improves time management abilities, some studies have linked it to results like job performance. The significance of time in literature has been increasingly acknowledged throughout the past 20 years.

According to Orlikowsky and Yates (2002), the time dimension of labor has become more significant due to growing global competitiveness and growing demands for immediate access to goods and services. Actions that are compressed (making a phone call while eating lunch), speed up chores, and reducing down on time spent (e.g., eating faster, sleeping less) are examples of the accelerated pace of life that. Employees experienced time pressure, according to a number of studies (e.g., Jackson & Martin, 1996; Major, Klein, & Ehrhart, 2002). Tracy (2000) views time as the secret to both personal and professional success, Helms and Ettkin (2000) view it as a weapon for competition. The amount of time required to recognize such issues and devise solutions. In order to achieve this, managers at all levels and in all organizational production or service systems should place a high value on the efficient use of human time in the work process (Buçinca, 2006).

Additionally, Ogundipe and Falade (2014) investigates the link between academic achievement and students' time management, concentrating on the amount of time spent on independent study, attending classes and seminars, and participating in group projects. According to their findings, academic success is positively correlated with

participation in classes, seminars, and independent study. At Ohio State University, Zulauf and Gortner (2000) employed a time diary survey and a specially created questionnaire to gauge each participant's time management practices. They came up with the result that good time management practices are positively correlated with GPA. According to Rai (2024), the proportion of students who complete their assignments on time is extremely low, and these students outperform those who struggle with time management. Oyuga et al. (2016) revealed similar findings for Kenyan secondary school orphans.

Pehlivan (2013) also found that students' grades were impacted by their ability to manage their time well. According to the report, Karadeniz Technical Institute students manage their time to a reasonable degree. In terms of the gender variable, female students outperform male students in terms of grades and time management. Bratti and Staffolani (2013) discovered how undergraduate students' academic performance was affected by both attending lectures and studying on their own. According to their findings, only lecture attendance has a positive correlation with success in quantitative subjects like mathematics and economics. For the majority of other courses, it is negligible.

There has been a lot of researches in Pakistani literature like Nasrullah and Khan (2015). examined the relation between time management and students' academic performance, including procrastination, workload pressure, distraction, and disorder to be significant factors. The survey found that successful students enjoyed good time management skills. Abu Saa et al. (2019) also highlights the variables effecting students' academic success. The dependent variable is the student's grade, whereas the independent factors are the student's age, gender, educational background, faculty, tuition trend, daily study hours, parents' socioeconomic status, educational medium, residential area, and housing trend. According to the study, academic performance is significantly correlated with both socioeconomic class and the number of hours spent studying each day.

The effect of students' time management on their academic performance was examined

by Mansha and Khanam (2023). They concentrate on pupils' long-term and short-term planning. According to the study's findings, students who manage their time well receive excellent grades, while those who don't do so receive low ones. Most students don't make plans and always spend their time in this manner, while just one-third of them make plans and work according to their priorities. Nasrullah and Khan (2015) examine how well students manage their time in order to meet academic requirements. Their results demonstrate a strong and favorable correlation between students' success and time management.

The idea for a time management training program was created by MacKenzie in 1954 and is still in use today. By teaching people how to prioritize tasks, develop daily plans, and deal with unforeseen chores, time management training programs seek to increase weekday efficiency, change time expenditure, and provide insight into time-consuming activities. Everyone now has access to time management training programs, books, and articles that were first created for managers. Despite the fact that emphasis on time management, comparatively little research has been done on the elements that contribute to an effective process that aims to maximize one's time (for example, by using one's important time to finish critical activities) and finish work on time.

Methodology

Objectives

1. To examine time management behavior as a predictor of perceived control of time among students.
2. To examine time management behavior as a predictor of life satisfaction of students.

Hypotheses

1. Time management behavior will positively predict perceived control of time among students.
2. Time management behavior will positively predict life satisfaction among students.

Sample

Three hundred students made up the study's sample. A sample of college and university students was chosen. Both male and female

students participated in the study. A purposive sampling approach was used to get the data. The participants were between the ages of 15 and 24 years.

Instruments

The scales listed below were applied. [1] Time management abilities were assessed using the 53-item Time Management Self-Assessment Questionnaire (Olmstead, 2010). The scale was a 5-point Likert type, with 1 representing never and 5 representing always. The reliability of the scale is satisfactory. [2] Perceived control of time was measured using the Perceived Control of Internal States Scale (Pallant, 2000), which consists of 18 items with a 5-point Likert-type response pattern, where 1 indicates strongly agree and 5 indicates strongly disagree. [3] A self-report survey measuring students' life happiness was the Students' Life Satisfaction Scale (Huebner et

al., 2022). The seven questions on the 6-point Likert-type scale where 1 indicates strongly disagree and 5 indicates strongly agree. The reliability of all scales were satisfactory.

Procedure

This study examined how students' time management behavior predicts perceived control over their time and life satisfaction using a cross-sectional research approach. To gather data from students, the researchers approached the relevant colleges and universities. Each student was given a brief explanation of the questionnaires. Prior to data collection, participants were also asked to fill out an informed consent form and give truthful replies. Additionally, the researchers ensured that all participant data would remain confidential. The researcher thanked the volunteers for their crucial contributions after data collection.

RESULTS

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics and Alpha Reliability of Study Variables

Scale	M	SD	Rang	Cronbach's α
Time Management Behavior	147.33	9.25	112-164	.73
Perceived Control of Time	18.57	4.35	7-25	.75
Student's Life Satisfaction	31.40	5.88	14-42	.71

Table 1 shows psychometric properties for the scale used in the present study. The Cronbach's α value for Time Management Behavior scale was .73 (<.80) which indicates moderate internal consistency. The Cronbach's α value for Perceived Control of

Time scale was .75 (<.80) which indicates satisfactory internal consistency. The Cronbach's α value for Student's Life Satisfaction scale was .71 (<.80) which indicates moderate internal consistency.

Table 2: Correlation for study variables

Variable	1	2	3
1. Time Management Behavior	-	.41**	.11*
2. Perceived Control of Time		-	.14*
3. Life Satisfactions of Student			-

* $p < .01$, ** $p < .01$

Table 2 reveals that time management has a significant positive correlation with perceived control of time ($r = .41$, $p < .01$) and significant positive relationship with life

satisfaction ($r = .11$, $p \leq .05$). Additionally, perceived control of time has a significant positive correlation with life satisfaction among students ($r = .14$, $p < .05$).

Table 3: Linear Regression Analysis of Time Management Behavior on Perceived Control of Time

Variable	B	β	SE
Constant	-9.98**		3.66
Time Management Behavior	.19**	.41	.02
R ²	.17		

** $p < .001$

Table 3 shows the effect of time management behavior on perceived control of time. The **R² value of .17** revealed that the predictor variable explained **17%** of the variance in the outcome variable, with **F (1,**

298) = 60.83, p < .01. The findings reveal that time management behavior positively predicts perceived control of time ($\beta = .41, p < .01$).

Table 4: Linear Regression Analysis of Time Management Behavior on Life Satisfaction of Students

Variable	B	β	SE
Constant	20.91**		5.40
Time Management Behavior	.07*	.11	.03
R ²	.01		

**p<.001

Table 4 shows the effect of time management behavior on life satisfaction of students. The **R² value of .01** indicates that the predictor explains **1%** of the variance in the outcome variable, with **F (1, 298) = 3.781, p < .01**. The findings reveal that time management behavior positively predicts life satisfaction among students ($\beta = .12, p \leq .01$).

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to investigate how time management behavior predicts perceived control of time and life satisfaction among students. In line with the expectations we discovered that time management behavior was positively predicted greater degree of perceived control of time and life satisfaction. The result is in line with earlier studies (e.g., Britton & Tesser, 1991; Claessens et al., 2004), which indicate that people who manage their time well are more likely to feel in control of their schedules. Earlier studies also indicate stress reduction and enhanced mental health are facilitated by a sense of control over one's schedule and well-organized time (Claessens et al., 2004; Rimsha, 2024). These results could be explained by the fact that productive time managers are better able to balance job, personal life, and leisure, which raises their sense of achievement and contentment with life. Furthermore, having more control over one's time may promote autonomy, lessen helplessness, and improve general wellbeing (Rothbaum et al., 1982).

Time management behavior positively predicted life satisfaction among students was also found in the current study. The result is consistent with other research (Macan, 1994; Naeem et al., 2024) that

highlights the significance of time management for mental health. Prior studies have looked at the connection between students' life happiness and their time management practices. According to the findings, students who were good at managing their time expressed greater levels of life satisfaction and a sense of control over their schedule (Naeem et al., 2024; Thongsri et al., 2024). Kuh (2008) found in another study that students' grades are positively impacted by how they allocate their time. Their grades improve when they devote enough time to learning and work as tutors or teacher assistants. Being a teacher assistant and showing up to all of the lessons requires a high degree of motivation, which is attained through time management.

Recommendations

To better understand the causal relationships between time management behavior, perceived control of time, and life satisfaction future research should use a longitudinal design. By following participants over time, researchers could investigate the long-term effects of shifts in time management practices or perceived control on life satisfaction and wellbeing. Qualitative methods like focus groups or interviews could also be used in future research to better understand why students typically report better time management practices than other students who do not. Future studies should concentrate on workshops and seminars and plan sessions for professionals, entrepreneurs, and students in Murree to enhance time management skills in order to test the findings' practical consequences.

Conclusion

It was found that time management behavior significantly positively predicted perceived control of time and life satisfaction among students. In summary, this study offers compelling evidence of the beneficial effects of time management practices and perceived time control on students' life satisfaction. The results highlight the value of time management abilities in enhancing well-being and imply that developing these abilities can assist students in leading more balanced and satisfying lives. All things considered, this study adds to the expanding corpus of research on time management and how it affects life satisfaction and provides useful advice for enhancing the wellbeing of students.

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